

OXIDATION BEHAVIOR OF CARBON/CARBON COMPOSITES COATED WITH A NOVEL LOW-COST SiC OXIDATION PROTECTION SYSTEM

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Abstract: In order to improve the oxidation behavior of carbon/carbon (C/C) composites in air at high temperatures, a new multilayer coating was developed. The SiC- borosilicate glass coatings with a thickness of about 200 μm were prepared on C/C composites. The microstructures and phase compositions of the coating were analyzed by SEM and XRD, respectively. The oxidation behavior of the coated composites in the temperature range from 900 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 1500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ was investigated by a thermobalance. The coating showed excellent oxidation protective ability and self-healing ability.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon/carbon (C/C) composites are widely applied in many industries, including aircraft, aerospace, metallurgy and biotechnology. C/C composites exhibit excellent high-temperature properties, such as high specific strength and modulus, and good thermal conductivity. However, the oxidation of C/C composites at temperatures above 400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ limits their use in air [1-5]. To solve this problem, SiC, Si_3N_4 , MoSi_2 and ZrB_2 etc. have been considered as possible coating materials for the C/C composites [6-7]. SiC is a promising candidate material at the temperatures below 1600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Compared with pack cementation, chemical and vapor deposition (CVD) [8], the fabrication technology of slurry and sintering has a lot of advantages including its easy processes and low costs.

In this study, a novel multilayer coating was developed. The SiC- borosilicate glass coating was prepared on C/C composite by a two-step technique. The microstructure and phase compositions of the coating were examined and also the oxidation behavior of the coated composite was investigated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Two dimensional C/C composites were used as substrates for coating. The SiC-borosilicate glass coating was prepared by the following steps: firstly, small specimens

used as substrates were cut from bulk C/C composites. The SiC layer was produced by slurry and sintering with direct chemical reaction between molten silicon and the C/C composite. After that, the borosilicate glass layer was prepared on the SiC coated C/C composites by slurry.

The crystalline structure and morphology of the coatings were analyzed using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Atomic percentages of components in the coating were evaluated by energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analysis coupled with SEM.

The oxidation resistance of the coated composites was evaluated in an air environment using a large-scale dynamic thermobalance. In the test, the specimens were heated to 900 °C, 1200 °C and 1500 °C for 120 min with the heating rate of 10 °C/min. The mass changes of the specimens were automatic and real-time measured by a balance system. The mass change (δ) was calculated by equation (1) [7].

$$\delta = (m_1 - m_0) / m_0 \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Where m_0 is the mass of the specimens before oxidation and m_1 is the mass after oxidation.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Phase composition and micro-structure of coating

The XRD pattern and SEM image of the SiC coating is given in Figure 1 (a)-(b). From Figure 1 (a), it is observed that the coating is composed of SiC. Figure 1 (b) shows the SiC coating is very dense and crack-free. The cross-section micrograph in Figure 1 (c) shows that the thickness of SiC-borosilicate glass coating was about 200 μm . It can be seen that the coating has a good combination with C/C substrate which can improve the performance of thermal shock resistance. There is also no obvious interface between SiC layer and borosilicate glass layer.

(a)

Figure 1: (a) XRD pattern of the specimen with SiC coating, (b) Surface micrograph of SiC coating, (c) Cross-section micrograph of SiC-borosilicate glass coating;

3.2 Oxidation test

Figure 2(a) shows the relation between mass change and oxidation time of the specimens with SiC-borosilicate glass coating at 900 °C、1200 °C and 1500 °C for 120 min. The mass gain of samples after oxidation at 900 °C、1200 °C and 1500 °C were 2.06%, 2.12% and 2.21%, respectively. Although they were affected by the individual, experimental conditions and environment, the absolute values were reasonable. During the isothermal oxidizing stage, the relative mass increase rates of samples were increased monotonously with the temperature increasing, which were 0.28%, 0.82% and 1.07%, respectively. According to the isothermal oxidation curves, the result shows that the mass change δ exhibited nearly an exponential decay function of the time. δ didn't have linearity relations or parabola relations with the exposing time, so it suggest that the oxidation behavior of the coating was both controlled by the diffusion of oxygen and oxidizing reactions. Hence, all of these reactions at high temperature can be described as follows:

When the reactions (2) and (3) are happened, the mass is increased because of oxidation products. In another way, if the reaction (4) is happened or the melting B_2O_3 and SiO_2 are evaporated, the mass is reduced. Figure 2(a) suggested that the oxidizing reactions were the major reactions during the isothermal oxidizing stage.

Figure 2(b)-(d) reveal the surface SEM micrographs of the coating after oxidation at 900 °C、1200 °C and 1500 °C for 120 min. It can be seen that there were no holes and cracks on the coatings and the surfaces were more smooth and dense with increasing temperature. At the temperature of 900 °C, the particles in glaze layer were just started to react and melt. When the temperature increased to 1500 °C, the oxidized product B_2O_3 and SiO_2 provided better liquidity and leveling, and sealed the holes and cracks. The kinetics of oxidation is limited by

oxygen permeability in the glassy phase. It is concluded that the borosilicate glass coating plays an important role in improving resistance to oxidation, where the coating shows excellent oxidation protective ability and self-healing ability.

Figure 2: (a) Relation between mass change and oxidation time of the specimen with SiC-borosilicate glass coating at different oxidation temperatures, Surface micrographs of coating after oxidation at (b) 900 °C for 120 min, (c) 1200 °C for 120 min, (d) 1500 °C for 120 min.

Figure 3 shows the cross-section micrograph of the coating after oxidation at 1500 °C and EDS mappings. The presence in the coating of the components of SiC and SiO₂, namely Si, C and O, was confirmed by EDS analyses. The oxygen amount was gradually distributed, which showed the oxygen permeability phenomenon.

Figure 3: Cross-section micrograph (a) of the coating after oxidation at 1500 °C with EDS mapping (b) Si, (c) O, (d) C.

Figure 4: Cross-section micrographs of SiC- borosilicate glass coating after oxidation at 1500 °C for (a) 10 min and (b) 120 min.

The coating thicknesses of two specimens after oxidation at 1500 °C for 10 min and 120 min were measured in the cross-section micrograph (Figure 4). The thickness of the coating after oxidating for 10 min was 180.1 μm and the thickness of the coating after oxidating for 120 min was 162.2 μm. It is obvious that the coating become thinner with the time extension. There are two possible explanations for the thickness change. One reason is that some oxidation occurred to make the coating much denser at high temperture, and the other cause is that the surfuac oxide layer was evaporated as the oxidizing reaction progress.

According to the results, it can be concluded that the oxidizing reaciontions are first happened at outer layer of the coating. With the oxygen diffusing, oxidized products get more. Meanwhile the oxidization layers can seal the holes and cracks, and limite the oxygen permeability. However, the melting B₂O₃ and SiO₂ are evaporated, so it can be speculated that the coating will be invalidated over long enough time at a high enough temperature.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A novel double layer SiC- borosilicate glass coating was prepared successfully on the surface of C /C composites. The coating layer was dense and crack-free. The obtained coating showed excellent anti-oxidation behavior in the temperature range of 900 °C to 1500 °C after 120 min oxidation. The weight increase rates of the coated sample were only about 2%. The oxidation behavior of the coating was both controlled by the diffusion of oxygen and oxidizing reactions. The SiC- borosilicate glass coated samples exhibit self-sealing performance and excellent oxidation protective ability due to the formation of glaze at high temperatuer. In all, this study may offer a new low-cost way to realize long-term protection for C/C composites applied in high-temperature condition.

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